

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF OFFLINE AND ONLINE LEARNING

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Online and offline forms of education are widely used in the modern educational process. With the development of technology, online education is becoming increasingly popular, but offline education hasn't lost its importance. Both methods have their own advantages and disadvantages, and their effectiveness depends on the needs, circumstances, and learning style of the learner. The demand for online education has increased dramatically in recent years. According to UNESCO, more than 1.5 billion students around the world switched to online education during the pandemic. This once again proves the power of online education. Offline education was introduced from March 15, 2020. Starting this year, online education began for universities and students. That is, they first learned to register on the Zoom platform, and then after the lessons, they learned to find and complete tasks given on various sites.

As we all know, in 2019, a financial crisis occurred all over the world. The reason for this was the COVID-19 virus. At the same time, in all higher education institutions around the world, the effective use of distance learning technologies was abandoned in order to ensure the continuity of students' education.

The traditional form of education, which is currently considered the most effective, is "offline" education. In this form of education, you will have the opportunity to communicate face to face with mentors and curators, network and make new friends, have more control, ask questions and get instant answers. Today's demand is to reform the educational process in the education system, develop teaching methods based on new information technologies, and widely implement them. In this regard, the introduction of a distance learning system is appropriate. The widespread use of the Internet in the early 1990s introduced a new direction in the world education system: "Distance learning". Distance learning is a method of distance learning, teaching, based on information and communication technologies: the Internet, e-mail, video conferencing, audio, video data and multimedia teaching aids. Distance learning requires constant active interactive learning from the student. This increases the

ABSTRACT

The rapid development of technology has brought about fundamental changes in the field of education. In particular, the transition from traditional offline (face-to-face) education to online education has reshaped the learning experience of students. Both learning methods have their own advantages and disadvantages, which significantly affect the attitude of students to the learning process and their effectiveness.

qualitative characteristics of the specialist's knowledge and skills. In distance learning, the teacher and student work at a considerable distance from each other. However, they are constantly in touch with each other through specially organized training courses, forms of control, communication methods using e-mail and other Internet technologies. Distance learning based on Internet technologies is a modern universal form of professional education, which is aimed at the individual needs of students and their specialties. Distance learning provides everyone with the opportunity to improve their professional level according to their individual abilities.

The coronavirus pandemic forced students from school to university to adopt online learning. This was welcomed by some and criticized by others. Online learning allows you to study remotely from anywhere, at convenient times, even at night. It also allows for more control over the pace of learning, and reduced costs (or savings on travel and lunch).

There are some students who do not learn well in a classroom setting. It is difficult to work with each of them individually in offline learning.

Online learning can address this problem. Because it is based on individual instruction and can work with the learner's pace. However, online learning also has some drawbacks:

Difficulty concentrating on a monitor or phone screen. One of the biggest problems with online learning for many students is maintaining focus on a screen for extended periods. For this reason, teachers must ensure their online lessons are engaging and interactive to keep the students' attention.

Technological issues. Another major problem with online lessons is internet access. While internet access is increasing in many parts of the world, there are still problems in rural areas.

Lack of interaction. Students learn a lot from their peers. However, online classes have minimal physical interaction between students and teachers. This often leads to a lack of understanding.

Teacher training needs. Many teachers have a very basic understanding of technology. Sometimes, they don't have the necessary resources or tools to deliver effective online lessons.

Screen time. Many parents worry about the health risks associated with their children spending many hours looking at screens. Increased screen time is one of the major concerns and disadvantages of online learning.

The biggest problem in traditional education is the use of a uniform teaching method for everyone.

Nowadays, the convenience of online education and its compatibility with modern technologies are attracting many people. However, the role and importance of offline education in human development still remains incomparable. Because education provides not only theoretical knowledge, but also the opportunity to develop personally, develop practical skills, communicate, and find one's place in the social environment.

Practical experience and real-life skills. The biggest advantage of offline education is the availability of practical training. For example, working with real equipment is very important in studying engineering, medicine, art, laboratory work, and other practical fields. Theoretical knowledge can be imparted in online education, but without practical training, this knowledge will not be sufficiently strengthened. Also, teamwork and seminar classes increase the student's logical thinking and problem-solving abilities.

Face-to-face communication and social development. Humanity is a social being by nature. The educational process takes place not only through lessons, but also through communication with people around them. In offline education, students have the opportunity to exchange ideas with each other, discuss, and work on team projects. Direct communication with teachers makes lessons more effective and understandable. In online education, these aspects are lacking or poorly developed.

Formation of a sense of discipline and responsibility. Offline education is based on strict discipline and develops students' qualities such as the correct distribution of time, timely

completion of assigned tasks. In the traditional education system, attendance at classes, timely submission of assignments, and teamwork are required. This teaches students to be responsible and organized. In online education, since students study independently, there is a high probability of procrastination.

Technical difficulties and lack of internet connectivity. Online education is completely dependent on the internet and technology. If the Internet quality is poor or devices such as computers and phones are not enough, it becomes difficult to get quality education. In addition, looking at the screen for a long time can be harmful to the eyes, make it difficult to concentrate, and reduce efficiency. In offline education, there are no such problems - classes are conducted in the traditional way, and students work with real books and notebooks.

Scientific environment and the opportunity to deeply absorb knowledge. In offline education, students are in a scientific environment and have the opportunity to use resources such as libraries, laboratories, and scientific circles of universities and schools. Online courses can provide theoretical information, but they do not provide much opportunity to engage in scientific research, study books, and work directly with professors and teachers. Also, in the traditional education system, students develop the skills to clearly express their thoughts, argue, and defend their opinions with scientific evidence.

Why should offline education be chosen? Practical exercises – Offline education allows you to reinforce theoretical knowledge with practical experience. Live communication and social development – Students learn more deeply by directly communicating with each other and teachers.

Discipline and responsibility – Students develop the habit of proper time management and responsible study. Avoidance of technical difficulties – Not being dependent on the Internet and technology makes the learning process seamless. Scientific environment and deep learning – Students learn deeply through libraries, laboratories, and academic environments. Online education can be convenient in certain circumstances, but offline education prevails as the most effective form of education. Because this system not only provides theoretical knowledge, but also comprehensively develops a person through practical skills, personal development, and social interaction.

Real education is not just about listening to lectures, but also about living with the environment, exchanging ideas with teachers and students, conducting scientific research, and gaining real-world experience. Therefore, if the goal is quality education, deep knowledge, and future success, offline education is the right choice.

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